

ISic4412

Epitaph for Aristoboula

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 23 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23439

Physical Description

Stele of the local stone, damaged below, forming part of an epymbion ('type B')

Dimensions

Height 50 cm

Width 30.5 cm

Depth 14.5 cm

Layout

Single line of Greek letters filling the width of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Slightly irregular letters, becoming slightly more compressed to the right hand end: Alpha broad with broken bar; rho has small closed eye; sigma is four equal bars, angled apart; omicron is small and mid-line; beta has equal closed eyes, with slight gap between them; upsilon asymmetrical.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Ἀριστοβούλας

Apparatus

text of Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Aristoboula

Commentary

The name Aristoboula [<http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/>

[igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF](http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF)

%CE%B2%CE%BF%CF%8D%CE%BB%CE%B1] is attested at Lipara (ISic4234 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4234]) and just outside Syracuse (ISic0825 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0825])

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4412>

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Bibliography

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Sofia, G. 2015. Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 116 fig.121

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